

Scale up of PHA production in a single-unit system with used cooking oil and a mixed microbial culture

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Abstract

The production of polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) using mixed microbial cultures (MMC) and waste as substrate, like used cooking oil (UCO), represents an innovative approach to reduce operational costs while valorising these residues. However, the main challenge when using oily substrates lies in the competition between PHA- and triacylglyceride- (TAG) storing populations, which can hinder high PHA production yields. In the present study, the feasibility of PHA synthesis with a MMC and UCO as substrate is evaluated at pilot-scale in a single-unit system (R1), where culture enrichment and PHA accumulation take place. Percentages of PHA accumulated inside the cells of 40 wt. % were achieved, while those of TAG remained at values of approximately 10 wt. %, indicating successful enrichment of PHA-storing populations. To further assess the potential of the enriched MMC, an additional accumulation unit (R2) was implemented downstream of R1. In R2, the enriched culture showed a capacity to synthesise PHA to values as high as 60 wt. %. Even so, the productivity in the single-unit reached a higher value (0.019 g PHA/(g UCO·h)) than that obtained in the two-unit system (R1 + R2) (0.013 g PHA/(g UCO·h)). These findings highlight the potential of a simplified single-unit process, serving as basis for a future industrialization.

Keywords

Mixed microbial culture; polyhydroxyalkanoates; pilot-scale; triacylglycerides; used cooking oil; valorisation.

INTRODUCTION

The evolution towards a circular economy will be possible if, among other things, the production of bio-based products with low environmental impact is promoted. Some of these bio-based materials are the polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs), which have plastic-like properties but with the biodegradability quality, emerging as adequate substitutes for conventional plastics. PHAs are produced by bacterial populations from a variety of carbon sources, including raw materials or wastes. Commonly, PHA production from wastes using mixed microbial cultures (MMC) involves three stages: (1) pretreatment of the waste (acidification to volatile fatty acids), (2) enrichment of the MMC with PHA-storing populations, and (3) PHA accumulation in the selected culture. When an oily waste is used as substrate, the pretreatment to obtain volatile fatty acids is not required as bacteria can directly use the fatty acids released from its hydrolysis.

Among the possible oily wastes that can be used, used cooking oil (UCO) stands out as a globally produced lipid waste for which the disposal process has not yet been optimised. In Spain, approximately 350 million liters of UCO are consumed per year, with only 5 % of those produced in households being recovered (Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación, 2023). The valorisation of UCO through the production of PHA is an under-researched process, with most studies focusing on pure cultures or even genetically modified bacteria (Loan et al., 2022; Ruiz et

al., 2019a; Kamilah et al., 2018).

Besides PHAs, the culture obtained fed with oily substrates can often accumulate triacylglycerides (TAGs), energy store lipids used as biodiesel. However, studies investigating the simultaneous synthesis of PHAs and TAGs are limited, both using pure (Hori et al., 2009) and mixed cultures (Argiz et al., 2022b). It has thus been observed that operating conditions influence the preference in the microbial culture for either PHA or TAG synthesis, leading to competition for the carbon source between the storage populations (Argiz et al., 2022a).

This research work evaluated the possibility of producing a PHA-storing MMC in a single-unit pilot-scale system using UCO as a carbon source. The study focused on combining the MMC enrichment and PHA accumulation stages within a single reactor, which could be an advantage for scaling up the technology.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Two sequential batch reactors (SBRs), each with a working volume of 24 L, were operated in series.

The first reactor (R1) was operated with hydraulic and solids retention times of 24 h (50 % of volume exchange ratio every 12 hours) for 133 days. In this unit, both the MMC enrichment and PHA accumulation took place. R1 was operated under aerobic dynamic feeding (ADF) conditions, with a feast/famine regime and a double growth limitation (DGL) strategy by uncoupling carbon and nitrogen sources supply. Activated sludge from a wastewater treatment plant was used as inoculum. The reactor operated in 12-hour cycles distributed as follows: UCO addition (1 pulse the first 30 days, and the same addition divided in 3 pulses separated by two hours from day 31 onwards), withdrawal (12 L), feeding of nutrient and nitrogen solution (12 L).

The second reactor (R2) received the effluent from R1 and served as an extra accumulation unit to study the maximum storing capacity of the single-unit. R2 operated also with 12-hour cycle distributed as follows: UCO addition in pulses every 2 hours (6 pulses, double the amount than in R1), withdrawal (12 L), and filling from R1 (12 L). The R2 operation of 74 days started on day 59 of R1.

Aeration was continuously supplied throughout the operational cycle using vacuum pumps (Laboport N 86 KTP, KNF Neuberger, USA) and diffusers located at the bottom and middle height of the reactors. The temperature was maintained at 30 °C by means of a thermal jacket connected to a thermostatic bath (Tectron Bio-100, JP Selecta, Spain).

The biomass from the reactors was characterized at the end of the feast phase on R1 and at the end of the cycle on R2. The total suspended solids (TSS) concentration was determined according to Standard Methods. The PHAs and TAGs accumulated were measured using the method described by Fra-Vázquez et al. (2018) slightly modified.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In R1, a biomass capable of accumulating PHA while maintaining a low percentage of TAG was successfully enriched. By operating this single-unit reactor, a PHA percentage ranging from 20 wt. % to 40 wt. % was achieved, while the TAG accumulation never exceeded 15 wt. % (Figure 1, A).

To further evaluate the potential of this enriched biomass, from day 59 onwards the extra accumulation unit (R2) was implemented. Results from R2 demonstrated that the selected biomass could accumulate higher PHA content reaching values up to 60 wt. %, while TAG content remained low (at approximately 10 wt. %) (Figure 1, B). These results showed that R1 is not optimized and the accumulation of PHA is limited by the cycle-length that constraint the UCO supplied during the feast.

Furthermore, in R2, the solids concentration reached values of 1.4 - 1.8 g TSS/L at the end of the cycle, compared to R1, where TSS concentration was between 0.4 and 0.6 g TSS/L at the end of the

feast phase (Figure 1, C). Meanwhile, in R1 the solids concentration is maintained through a constant dilution and duplication over the cycles, R2 have a higher solids concentration because they are received from R1 and accumulated without a duplication of them. The last days of R1 and R2 operation showed a consistent trend in the measured parameters that indicate the stability of the system.

Figure 1. Accumulation of the PHA (%) (\ominus) and the TAG (%) (\oplus) at the end of the feast phase of R1 (A), production of them at the end of cycle of R2 (B) and TSS at the end of feast phase (\ominus) of R1, and at the end of cycle of R2 (\oplus) (C).

When relative stable conditions of the system were reached (day 100 of operation onwards), the productivity of the single-unit system (R1) was compared to the two-unit one (R1 + R2) (Table 1). In terms of volumetric productivity, the two-unit configuration showed a better result (0.018 g PHA/(L·h)), although the specific productivity was better in the single-unit system (0.017 g PHA/(g TSS·h)). Finally, if the PHA produced by the system per amount of UCO used is studied, R1 shows again a better performance with 0.019 g PHA/(g UCO·h).

Table 1. Comparative results of the process for day 105 of the two configurations R1 (single-unit) and R1 + R2 (two-units).

	TSS (g/L)	PHA (%)	TAG (%)	HRT (h)	g UCO/cycle	Productivity		
						Volumetric (g PHA/(L·h))	Specific (g PHA/(g TSS·h))	Substrate (g PHA/(g UCO·h))
R1	0.56	40.06	4.07	24	12	0.009	0.017	0.019
R1 + R2	1.77	48.91	13.07	48	33	0.018	0.010	0.013

As described in previous studies, uncoupled carbon and nitrogen feeding (DGL strategy) helps with the preferential selection of PHA-storing populations over the TAG-accumulating ones (Argiz et al., 2022a) as observed during R1 operation (Figure 1, B). Moreover, with the single-unit system, the maximum accumulation of PHA was reached on day 105 with 40.06 wt. % (Figure 1, A) and 0.56 g TSS/L (Figure 1, C). These results are considerably higher than those reported in previous studies using a similar reactor configuration and oily waste (25 wt. % of PHA and 0.5 g TSS/L) (Argiz et al. 2022b). Besides this, the pulse feeding strategy applied in the present research also helps the PHA accumulation. From day 30 onwards, a marked increase in PHA accumulation was observed, aligning with findings from previous studies that attribute this improvement to a lower carbon influx (Argiz et al., 2022b). In comparison with existing studies in the present research the enrichment on PHA-storing populations was achieved without the necessity of a substrate pretreatment that in some cases lead to a saponification of the waste (Ruiz et al., 2019b).

CONCLUSION

The present study demonstrates the ability to obtain, in a single-unit system using UCO as a carbon source, a MMC enriched in PHA-storing populations with a PHA storage capacity of up to 40 wt. %. Moreover, the addition of a subsequent accumulation unit showed that the capacity of the culture for the bioproduct accumulation was higher, so the results could be improved by optimising the process. Although the PHA productivity obtained by just one unit was higher in terms of solids (0.017 g PHA/(g TSS·h)) and substrate (0.019 g PHA/(g UCO·h)), the volumetric productivity

resulted higher in the two-units system (0.018 g PHA/(L·h)). Nevertheless, this study with pilot-scale reactors, which lacks research, showed promising results for process scale-up and future industrialization.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was supported by the Spanish Government (AEI) through the ECOPOLYVER project [MACROPOLYVER PID2020-112550RB-C21] and the project POLYGO1 [TED2021-130164B-I00 / AEI / 10.13039 / 501100011033 / Unión Europea NextGenerationEU / PRTR]. Alba Pedrouso acknowledges the Xunta de Galicia (Spain) for her postdoctoral fellowship (ED481D-2024-010). The authors belong to a Galician Competitive Research Group (GRC ED431C 2021/37), programme co-funded by FEDER (EU). Also, the network HOLIWATER (RED2022-134350-T) funded by MCIN/AEI is thanked

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